

APPROACH TO CONTROL OF FIBRE ORIENTATION BY RESTRICTION AT FLOW FRONT IN INJECTION MOULDING

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ABSTRACT

The fibre orientation of a product depends to the flow pattern in the mould after the applied process. It is difficult but important to predict and control the fibre orientation in injection moulding of FRTP (Fibre Reinforced Thermo-Plastics) in behaving the flow under special purpose. The method in this paper could be developed by controlling on the potentiality of restriction at the flow front during the moulding process. It can be concluded that this restriction created only a stable flow front but also allowed the entire body to become stable. The control system developed on the fibre orientation could be applied practically, since the analytical consideration on this paper are verified by the experimental results.

INTRODUCTION

Injection moulding is substituted for conventional materials in manufacturing products, because of its quality and productivity, that is, have good specific stiffness and strength. However the method still has many problems, such as brittle weakness along the weld-line and warp caused by the fibre orientation during the thermal diffusion process.

The fibre orientation of a product, dependent on the flow pattern caused by canal configuration in the mould, could not controlled in injection moulding of FRTP. This is especially so in the case of using a complex die configuration except changing the location of the gate. In spite of the difficulty, it is important to predict and control the fibre orientation in order to prevent a warp, that is, out of plane displacement and to improve the rigidity of the product in the necessary part.

Since the fibre orientation depends on the flow pattern, the method could be developed by controlling the restriction at the flow front during injection moulding. The investigation in this paper on cylindrical products of FRTP is being conducted as a simplified case.

INTERPRETATION OF FLOW BEHAVIOUR PREDICATED ON FIBRE ORIENTATION IN EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Experiments were carried out as an object on cup shape product being fabricated by transfer moulding process as shown in Fig.1 instead of injection moulding caused by small quantity products in experiment.

The slide ring was arranged in the cylindrical cavity of the model instrument to control the shift of flow front. It could be obtained the suitable fibre orientation with a view to this paper to apply a counter pressure by spring shown in the figure. Fibre orientation is observed with soft x-ray photography. Because carbon fibres are invisible under X-ray radiation, tracers, made from copper electro-plated fibres,

Fig.1 Schematic diagram of the model instrument.

Fig.2 Shape and dimension of the specimen.

were used.

Experience has shown that the similar characteristics was observed after moulding behaviour in applying glass fibre as reinforcement in the case of until 20 weight % of content. To interpret the configuration of fibre orientation in component with the object of decreasing effect of skin layer independently, polyethylene with trace fibre is applied to analyse the behaviour of high polymer and fibre orientation influenced by circumstances caused by above reason.

The distribution of the fibre orientation in the disk gate is observed on concentric circles as shown in Fig.3. The solid line shown in this diagram are drawn so that the direction gives the mean orientation of the fibre and the length shows the orientation factor. It might be easy understood the rigid rotation of fibre after moulding depend on the configure ration of canal in the mould by considering the extrusion ratio, that is, the ratio of inlet area of A_0 to that of the extruded of A and shown $R = A_0/A$

The fibre orients along the stream line for $R \geq 1$, and rotates perpendicular to the line for $R < 1$, that is, spread way as disk gate.

The distributions of fibre orientation in the cylindrical canal part are shown as two different patterns as in Fig.4 (a) or (b) in case of the same thickness with gate disk and cylindrical wall for the free flow front condition. The tangentially orientation on the fibre at the circumference of disk gate might be ordinarily brought in cylindrical entrance and shifted into flow direction since R is equivalent to unit, in the case as shown in Fig.4 (a). As the configuration of jointed has an appearance of from spread to parallel cylindrical path, the fibre orientation in the latter path might be arranged along the stream line, since the junction part is supposed as a converge phase being expanded two dimensional. One of the result is shown in Fig.4(b).

Fig.3 Diagram of the orientation in the disk gate.

(thickness of gate: $t=2.5\text{mm}$, cross-head speed: $cs=50\text{mm/min}$, controlling flow front(C.F.))

Fig.4 Diagram of the orientation in the specimen in case of free flow front. (t=2.5mm, cs=50mm/min)

Fig.5 Diagram of the orientation in the specimen after controlling flow front. (t=2.5mm, cs=50mm/min, C.F.)

The flow state of each type in the experimental results shown (a) and (b) in Fig.4 are interpreted to keep track of the plot according to the segments placed end to end for the measurement of fibre orientation in both figures and should consider the influence depended on the next columns of segments. The first and second row might show an unstable flow condition and the development of state affairs as flow front for above cases are caused by a distribution of material stiffness along the rows.

Cup shape product is generally requested to resist a hoop stress caused by arranged fibre orientation in the direction of circumference. The method controlling the flow front by the slide ring has been developed to attain the object. The result is obtained without fail as shown in Fig.5.

Secondly, experiments are carried out with various and larger thickness of the disk gate than the cylindrical wall. The fibre orientation diagram in the case of 9 mm of disk gate thickness is observed in Fig.6 that the direction of the fibre orientation are parallel to flow direction, since the value of R is considered to be greater than unit in the boundary domain.

Finally it is attempted to develop the method of controlling the fibre orientation by the instrumentation of temperature gradient system being given the cooling pipes at the regular circumferential positions toward the flow direction. The results of the fibre orientation diagram are shown in Fig.7 in which the case of the controlling of fibre orientation applying the slide ring to restrict the flow front and of the free front without the slide ring are shown in Fig.7 (a) and Fig.7 (b) respectively. And the edges of right and left are lower and the centre is higher on temperature gradient of the diagrams in the figure. The extrusion ratio at the transposition domain from disk gate to cylindrical cavity in the figures is less than unit, therefore the fibre orientation has a tendency to arrange in circumferential direction for steady flow condition shown as in Fig.7 (b). And after careful attention to the configuration of fibre orientation in the diagram, it is understood that the complex formation of flow front and the rigid rotation of the fibre to flow direction according to the higher temperature domain during the process. In spite of above mentioned complex condition, the arrangement of fibre orientation could be attained semi-regular condition as shown in Fig.7 (a) by applying the slide ring to control a flow front.

Fig.6 Diagram of the orientation in the specimen. (t=9.0mm, cs=50mm/min, C.F.)

(a) In case of controlling flow front

(b) In case of free flow front

Fig.7 Diagram of the orientation in the specimen with temperature gradient. (t=1.0mm, cs=50mm/min)

FLOW ANALYSIS^{1,2}

The flow state of the composite material is analyzed two-dimensionally in the core layer, taking into consideration on the friction against the upper and lower skin layers during moulding.

An injection moulded product is considered to consist of skin and core layers in the thickness direction, the thin skin layer has approximately constant thickness and the fibre orientation is random and has little influence on the overall properties. This is confirmed by experiments. Considering the flow to be isothermal due to the insulating effect of the skin layers, the following motion (1) and continuity (2) equations for unsteady, incompressible and two-dimensional pseudo-plastic flow are used as governing equation.^{3,4}

$$\rho \frac{d\mathbf{v}}{dt} = - \frac{\partial P}{\partial \mathbf{x}} + K [4 | \Pi_e |]^{(n-1)/2} \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{v}}{\partial \mathbf{x}_i \partial \mathbf{x}_i} + \rho \mathbf{F} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial v_k}{\partial x_k} = 0 \quad (2)$$

where $\Pi_e = - \{ 1/2 (e_{11}^2 + e_{22}^2) + e_{12}^2 \}$, $e_{ij} = 1/2 (v_{i,j} + v_{j,i})$, ρ is the density, \mathbf{v} is the velocity, \mathbf{F} is the traction, p is the pressure, K is the pseudo-plastic viscosity, n is the power exponent, e_{ij} is the rate of deformation tensor and Π_e is the invariant. The frictional resistance against the upper and lower skin layers is assumed to be the body force as follows,

$$\mathbf{F}_i = -2 \cdot \beta \cdot \mathbf{v} \sqrt{\{v_i \cdot v_i\}} / T_{c,i} \quad (3)$$

where β is the frictional coefficient and $T_{c,i}$ is the thickness of the core layers. The finite element method (the method of weighted residual of Galerkin) is used to solve the integration in space and the finite differential method is used to solve the integration in time.

The examples of the boundary conditions and the finite division are shown in Fig.8. Considering the formulation of the skin layer, the flow rate is reduced at the element along the flow front. Examples of the results of velocity vectors and pressure

Fig.8 Boundary condition for flow analysis.

distribution are shown in Fig.9 (a),(b).

FIBRE ORIENTATION ANALYSIS

After the flow state analysis, the fibre orientation analysis is carried out, where it is assumed that the fibre orientation depends solely upon the flow of the resin.

At the initial condition, the number of fibres corresponding to the fibre content, oriented randomly, are applied at the entrance. The fibre are tracked throughout the moulding process, rotating according to the velocity gradient tensor obtained in each element from the numerical results of the above flow state analysis considering the scale factor in the coordinate system related to the extrusion ratio.

An example of the numerical result are shown in Fig.9 (c) for comparison with the experiment (shown in Fig.5 considering a restriction for progress of flow front). It is found that the numerical analysis of the fibre orientation is useful in case of controlling the flow front by the slide ring.

DISCUSSION

The velocity gradient arise along a fibre and it is found that a fibre is turned which is perpendicular to flow direction because the flow condition in the disk gate is radial flow ($R < 1$). When thickness of gate is thicker than one of cylindrical wall ($R > 1$), the flow to cylindrical part

(a) Velocity vectors

(b) Pressure distribution

(c) Fibre orientation

Fig.9 Results of the numerical analysis.
($t=2.5\text{mm}$, Initial velocity=200mm/sec,
Time=5.314sec)

is the contraction flow and it is found that a fibre is turned which is parallel to flow direction.

It seems that the disordered fibre orientation in case of the free flow front is caused that the disturbance, such as the refuse and flaw on surface of a cavity, disordered the flow condition. In case of the free flow front, it is found that the orientation distribution is variable by temperature gradient on the wall surface of a cavity.

It is found that fibre orientation is stabilized by controlling the flow front using the slide ring in spite of disturbance such as refuse, flaw and temperature gradient. Because the results of the fibre orientation analysis agrees with the results in case of controlling the flow front, this analysis can predict the stabilized fibre orientation on this control system. It may be possible that the design of mould and product is taken into consideration of the fibre orientation, applying this method of controlling the flow front and this numerical analyses.

CONCLUSION

The following results are obtained,

- (1) By controlling the flow front, it is found that the steady cavity filling process can achieve the desired fibre orientations.
- (2) The fibre orientation in cylindrical product wall is controlled by the thickness of the disk gate.
- (3) In the numerical analysis, the fibre orientation in case of controlling flow front is predicted sufficiently.

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